

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TECHNOLOGIES ON TEACHING EFL LESSONS

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Abstract: In the article concerning the development of research on the dissemination of network and information technologies in the sphere of education. The author comes to the conclusion that information technologies have an impact on education generally and on teaching foreign languages in particular. The Internet, as an information system, provides a wealth of knowledge and tools for designing the educational process in an efficient manner. It is acknowledged that contemporary students receive a superior quality education due in part to the use of information and network technology. The article points out that new methods for teaching English and improving speaking and listening abilities have emerged as a result of contemporary perspectives on learning outcomes.

Key words: information, technology, listening, speaking, educational activity, survey, manifest, grades, network technologies, diversity, efficiency, didactic tasks, skills.

Introduction

It is hard to envision modern life without a computer. Every aspect of human existence and activity are impacted. The field of Internet communication emerged in connection with the introduction of computers into a network and the development of the Internet. Due in part to the information problems of the modern world, modern society places extra requirements on students' educational backgrounds.

Materials and methods

The use of technology in language teaching has been increasing and is considered an important educational tool across various teaching and learning environments. It provides many potential opportunities to enhance the content and delivery of pedagogical methods, especially in English language teaching. The application of modern technology represents a significant advance in contemporary English language teaching methods.

Various technologies can be used in English language teaching, including computers, mobile devices, Learning Management Systems (LMS), and different media types. The choice of technology should be based on its compatibility with the teaching and learning objectives associated with courses or individual units.

Teaching with technology offers several benefits, such as providing unlimited resources to language learners, enhancing content and delivery of pedagogical

methods, and offering opportunities for students to gain practice, confidence, and development, especially for ESL students. Technology provides learners with access to authentic materials, improves digital literacy, and allows for student-centered methods of teaching, which are more effective for digital natives.

Studies have shown that integrating technology in teaching English as a foreign language has been increasing, with a growing number of studies conducted in recent years. This trend indicates that technology integration in teaching English as a foreign language is becoming more important year by year.

Results and discussion

Language teaching through technology highlight the significant impact of technology on language learning and teaching methods. Various sources emphasize the benefits and implications of integrating technology into language education:

1. Enhanced Learning Environment: Technology-driven learning environments create flexible spaces with connected devices, audiovisual tools, and purposeful furniture that engage students positively and support a mix of learning styles.

2. Diverse Teaching Methods and Resources: Technology enables a wider range of language teaching methods by utilizing multimedia, communicative approaches, educational games, and various resources to enhance students' exposure to the target language.

3. Real-World Connection: New technologies like videos, images, and software solutions allow teachers to bring real-world contexts into the classroom, motivating students to practice and immerse themselves deeply in the language.

4. Efficiency in Lesson Planning: Technology provides tools and platforms that help teachers plan, organize, and share lessons more efficiently, saving time and enhancing organization through learning management systems and dedicated language teaching platforms.

5. Continuous Professional Development: Technology offers opportunities for continuous professional development through online courses, instructional videos, webinars, and e-conferences, allowing language teachers to enhance their skills and knowledge.

6. Wider Exposure and Cultural Contexts: Technology provides students with wider exposure to the target language and cultural contexts, facilitating authentic interactions with native speakers and other learners to enhance language proficiency.

7. Higher Motivation and Attention: Technology transforms students from passive recipients to active learners, increasing motivation and attention during language courses through interactive multimedia features and voice recognition tools.

8. Flexible Learning: Technology offers students more freedom within the classroom to decide how they approach language learning, promoting self-decision

making and individual responsibility-taking for a more enriching linguistic immersion.

9. Adaptive Learning: Technology enables the creation of adaptive learning systems that track students' progress, adjust lessons, and provide tailored learning experiences, allowing students to learn at their own pace and focus on areas needing improvement. The integration of technology in language teaching enhances the learning environment, provides diverse teaching methods and resources, connects learning to the real world, improves efficiency in lesson planning, supports continuous professional development, offers wider exposure to language and cultural contexts, boosts motivation and attention, enables flexible learning, and facilitates adaptive learning experiences for students.

Conclusion

Based on the research data, it is clear that network technologies can provide students with several benefits in language teaching. These include differentiation and individualization of learning, development of independence and creativity, access to new sources of educational information, and creation of conditions for the manifestation and development of students' subjectivity. Moreover, network technologies offer numerous benefits for language teaching, including differentiation and individualization of learning, development of independence and creativity, access to new sources of educational information, and creation of conditions for the manifestation and development of students' subjectivity. By integrating network technologies into language teaching, educators can provide a more dynamic, engaging, and effective learning experience for students.

References:

1. Basova A.V. To the question of writing and written speech in teaching a foreign language: methods of teaching foreign languages / A.V. Basov. - 96 Kb. - Yaroslavl: Publishing House of YaGPU named after. K.D. Ushinsky, 2006 // Language. Culture. Education: Collection of materials of the international scientific conference "Readings of Ushinsky". - 2006. - Issue. 2. - 160 p. - (For English teachers).
2. Mukhametzyanova F. G., Panchenko O. L., Khairutdinov R. R. Magistracy as a methodological phenomenon: challenges of modernity // Person and education. 2017. - No. 3 (52). - P. 9-14.
3. Mukhametzyanova F.G., Panchenko O.L. Subjectivity in the interdisciplinary discursive field // Kazan Pedagogical Journal. 2018.– No. 2 (127). - P. 12-16.
4. Mynbaeva A.K. Innovative teaching methods, or how it is INTERESTING TO TEACH: study guide / A.K. Mynbaeva, Z.M. Sadvakasova. - 4th ed., add. - Almaty. - 2010. - 344 p.

5. Polat E.S. Internet at foreign language lessons//Foreign languages at school. - 2001. - No. 2. - S. 17-28.

6. Selevko G.K. Pedagogical technologies based on information and communication tools / G. K. Selevko. - M.: Research Institute of School Technologies, 2005. -208 p.

7. Ushnitskaya V.V. Multimedia technologies in teaching English// New technologies in education: Scientific and methodological conferences of YSU. Theses.reports - 2008 - from 91-93.